

EDEN ISS

D4.4 – Overall System Test Report

prepared for

WP 4.4 – Overall System AIT

Version: 1.0

Published: 2018-09-28

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Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
0.1	2018-04-03	M. Bamsey	Initial draft
0.2	2018-05-03	See author list	Complete draft
1.0	2018-09-28	See author list	Minor updates. Release version

Executive summary

The overall system test report describes the preparation, execution and results of the assembly, integration and test phase. In particular this document provides details on:

- AIT infrastructure
- AIT phase timeline
- Subsystem results, issues that surfaced and design lessons learned
- Overall test phase results
- De-integration and shipment preparation

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AIT	Assembly, Integration and Test	ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack
AMS	Atmosphere Management System	LED	Light Emitting Diode
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute	MCC	Mission Control Center
C&DH	Command and Data Handling	MTF	Mobile Test Facility
DLR	German Aerospace Center	NDS	Nutrient Delivery System
EC	Electrical Conductivity	NM-III	Neumayer Station III
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	RH	Relative Humidity
FMECA	Failure Modes, Effects and Criticality Analysis	SES	Service Section
FRR	Flight Readiness Review	TCS	Thermal Control System
ILS	Illumination System	UV	Ultraviolet

1 AIT Campaign Infrastructure

The EDEN ISS AIT campaign occurred at the DLR Institute of Space Systems in Bremen. The AIT campaign involved access not just to the EDEN ISS MTF, but to various DLR facilities and infrastructure installed specifically for the campaign. In particular the following primary elements were employed:

- EDEN ISS MTF including AIT tent
- EDEN ISS integration laboratory
- EDEN ISS Mission Control Center
- The nominal EDEN laboratory

These various elements are described in detail in the sections to follow.

1.1 MTF Externally Installed Location

The MTF was installed behind the DLR Institute of Space System main office building as illustrated in Figure 1. This install location, in close proximity to the office building, offered ease of access from the EDEN ISS project integration laboratory and nominal EDEN laboratory (both located in the office building), quick access to the MTF for visiting subsystem leads and DLR employees participating in the integration phase (in contrast to an install location behind the DLR laboratory building which is several hundred meters away) and has direct line of sight to the DLR EDEN ISS Mission Control Center.

Figure 1: MTF location during the AIT campaign (indicated by the arrow).

The location of the MTF during the AIT campaign is further illustrated on a drawing of the property of the DLR Institute of Space Systems in Figure 2.

Figure 2: DLR Bremen site plan with approximate location of the MTF indicated by the red rectangle.

A view from the ground of the specifically planned MTF install location is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Ground level view of the MTF location (taped-out area).

In addition to the MTF containers, a large tent was installed outside of the main entrance to the MTF (Figure 4). The tent was used to protect equipment during the final steps before installation in the MTF, while also providing an enlarged work space for the integration team during the AIT campaign. The tent included indoor lighting and housed a number of work tables and tools. The tent was raised off the ground via a wooden platform. The tent was particularly important during the winter months of the AIT phase.

Figure 4: The installation of the wooden tent platform with the AIT tent in the background.

1.2 EDEN ISS Integration Laboratory

A newly obtained laboratory in the DLR Institute of Space Systems office building was employed for the final preparation of subsystems before their integration into the MTF. Hardware shipped to DLR would often undergo post-shipment testing within this laboratory to ensure that it remained functional. This laboratory, shown in Figure 5, provided the appropriate tools for the subsystem tests and provided a cleaner environment compared to the external integration tent. Following sufficient testing, subsystems/components were transferred from the laboratory to the MTF.

Figure 5: The EDEN ISS integration laboratory soon after acquisition.

1.3 EDEN ISS DLR Mission Control Center

During the AIT phase the project team also transformed a large meeting room on the top floor of the DLR Institute of Space Systems into the EDEN ISS Mission Control Center (Figure 6). This was a large activity but the facility serves as a vital connection link between Europe and the MTF in Antarctica.

Figure 6: The EDEN ISS Mission Control Center at the DLR Institute of Space Systems in Bremen, Germany.

The facility was thoroughly tested during the AIT phase and displays project data, imagery and is used for regular video links between the DLR team and the on-site operator.

1.4 Nominal EDEN Laboratory

Although none of the larger AIT activities were planned within the DLR EDEN team's laboratory, the laboratory was used for testing of some MTF hardware as well as project selected cultivars. As this facility will remain a functional laboratory throughout the EDEN ISS project, it will continue to serve as an operational environment where certain equipment can be deployed and tested for possible future upgrades to the MTF.

2 Assembly, Integration and Test Phase Results

2.1 Overview of Timeline

The EDEN ISS subsystem integration phase commenced with the delivery of custom-built shipping containers to DLR at the beginning of October 2016. From here all necessary subsystems were installed, beginning with the internal structural elements of the Service Section (SES) and the Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG). The Nutrient Delivery System (NDS), Illumination System (ILS), and the Atmosphere Management System (AMS) were installed in the months to follow.

Figure 7 presents a detailed overview of the main activities and timeline of EDEN ISS Assembly, Integration and Test (AIT) phase. The Thermal Control System (TCS) was delivered in December 2017 and its integration was finalized at the beginning of February 2017 when the TCS free cooler system was initially connected to the ILS and the AMS. In April 2017, the furniture within the Service Section was installed, allowing the team to use the work station for later facility and plant production procedures. Right after the accomplishment of the internal work station, the International Standard Payload Rack (ISPR) (ISS rack-like plant growth system) was delivered and integrated into the Service Section. Beginning February 2017, the Mission Control Center (MCC) was built up and was continuously improved in the coming months, until it was operational in mid-July 2017.

Figure 7: Overview of EDEN ISS project activities from the first AIT activities to the end of the deployment mission.

After a full system test during mid-May, the first plants were included into the system at the beginning of June 2017. The project Flight Readiness Review (FRR) meeting was held from the 28th to 29th of June at DLR Bremen site. This way the consortium partners, the European Union evaluation board, and the internal EDEN ISS scientific advisory board had the opportunity to visit the MTF during a nominal grow-out phase and raise any final issues that could be acted on prior to the conduct of the deployment mission. The testing phase, including the grow-out trials of plants, continued until the end of August 2017. This period also included initial tests of the scientific equipment for microbial, food quality and safety investigations which provided training and teach-in opportunities for the associated procedures that would be conducted during the deployment mission by the EDEN ISS overwintering crew member (Paul Zabel). Almost concurrently, the required training for the Alfred-Wegener-Institute for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)-coordinated overwintering crew started. The training comprised extensive first aid courses, fire-fighting courses, NM-III station operation procedures and a several day survival/mountaineering course in the Alps. The EDEN ISS on-site crew member was trained, together with the regular nine AWI station crew members usually foreseen for the isolation phase.

End of August 2017, the system test and grow-out phase was concluded in order to start with the mission preparation phase. All plants within the FEG were harvested, regardless of the present lifecycle stage, in order to begin with extensive cleaning procedures. The clean-up phase took roughly one month, where all remaining biomass was removed from the MTF, the nutrient supply lines were

cleaned and dried out, and all surfaces were wiped and disinfected accordingly. Finally, the Trans-MADD system, which was developed by the consortium partner Airbus Defence and Space was deployed within the MTF in order to disinfect the remaining and hard-to-reach areas within the facility by emitting a 12% hydrogen peroxide aerosol.

In mid-September all connections (fluid, thermal, data, and power) between the two containers of the MTF were disconnected and the two containers were separated from each other. Both containers were sealed with a removable transportation wall in order to allow safe transport via ship. Further, the packing of all essential supplies, spares, and scientific equipment took place during the mission preparation phase. A dedicated 20 foot transport container, provided by AWI, served as main transport- and storage unit for this additional mission equipment as well as for external MTF hardware (e.g., free cooler, step ladders, and external lights). On October 2nd 2017, the two MTF containers and the storage container were picked up in order to begin their journey to Antarctica. After this important milestone, additional last minute equipment was combined into a dedicated air freight shipment, allowing the team to send additional (small) items via airplane to the NM-III station. At the beginning of December, the EDEN ISS containers arrived in Cape Town, South Africa and were transferred onto the S.A. Agulhas II for the last step of their transport.

The deployment team arrived in Cape Town mid-December and flew in to NM-III on December 17th, which marked the beginning of the on-site deployment mission. Due to organizational and weather-related difficulties, the final offloading of the EDEN ISS containers at Antarctica was shifted to January 3rd, 2018. After connecting the MTF containers on the platform, the internal subsystem integration took place, followed by an overall system test. Then, at the beginning of February 2018, the first plants were inserted into the MTF. Mid-February 2018, the deployment team departed the station and the on-site crew member began with the nominal operations within the greenhouse.

All the listed timeline dates (save the milestones) need to be considered as rough points in time. This means that several activities were also continued after their official planned end point. This is owed to the fact that during this time unplanned repairs, component exchanges and improvements had to be implemented, which further shifted the actual completion of a certain activity.

2.2 Subsystem Results

2.2.1 Air Management System

The first step of the AMS installation was the installation of the subfloor air ducts in the Service Section. These were installed by the DLR EDEN ISS team in the middle of October, 2016. The bulk of the AMS was installed during two different partner on-site phases:

- Week of Jan 30th, 2017
 - Personnel: Engineer from Aero Sekur/Arescosmo and technician from CLR, Italy
 - Main activities:
 - AMS delivered as integrated rack
 - Installed main rack components, CO₂ distribution system
- Week of Mar 6, 2017
 - Personnel: Engineer from Aero Sekur/Arescosmo and technician from CLR, Italy
 - Main activities:
 - Installation of flexible ducts, initial condensate collection system

It was realized several months prior to the AIT phase, when planning the integration sequence of the two EDEN ISS containers, that the Service Section subfloor air ducts would need to be installed as one of the very first elements. In particular, this was because of the fact that the subfloor air ducts came in sections and, due to the layout of the subfloor support structure; these would not be able to be installed after the installation of the power and NDS racks (when the containers were already joined. If the containers were still separate the installation of the subfloor air ducts posed no issues,

even with racks already installed). Thus the subfloor air ducts were delivered early in the AIT phase and installed on Oct 13, 2016 as seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The installed Service Section subfloor air duct.

The installation of the bulk of the AMS was then reinitiated in January 2017. Figure 9 presents images of the AMS following the initial installation phase and following the second Aero Sekur/Arescosmo and CLR partner visit.

Figure 9: The appearance of the AMS following initial integration (left) and in its operational configuration (right).

Additional AMS activities continued throughout the AIT phase based upon what was learned during the early operations. The primary observations from the system during the installation and test phase included:

Condensate collection system leak: Although this was not immediately observed during AMS operations as there were no crops yet within the FEG, upon the installation of a humidifier in the FEG to provide for the addition of water vapour to the air, it was observed that the AMS rack was leaking the collected condensate. Figure 10 and Figure 11 illustrate the location of the condensate leak.

Figure 10: Screenshot from a video illustrating the leak of captured condensate just after the heat exchanger.

Figure 11: CAD model with a red arrow depicting the location of the AMS condensate leak.

The condensate leak was the most concerning of any observed AMS issues during the Bremen test phase. This was the case, as this part of the AMS rack was not constructed to be removed from the AMS system. Removing the entire rack to provide access to the heat exchanger and water droplet separator was considered but deemed too labour intensive as it would have set the team back ca. 4-5 days. The team instead decided to use an angle grinder to cut out the section in question. This section was subsequently tested for leakage by spraying water into the possible leaking interfaces and this allowed the specific leak location to be determined. Considerably more insulation was added and better positioned with respect to the fastener holes in the two pieces being integrated (Figure 11). The section was then re-tested on the lab bench and subsequently re-installed within the AMS rack. The resulting work load was approximately two days, and in the end provided a more robust final solution that now allows for the Antarctic operator to access a greater subset of the AMS rack parts in a modular manner.

Addition of an air release valve at the top of the AMS: Based on experience with other systems in the laboratory and with the FEG LED water cooling lines, it was deemed necessary to install an air release

at the high point of the AMS heat exchanger. This post-installation design modification was added as shown in Figure 12. Since its installation it has been used on numerous occasions to ensure that air was fully out of the AMS heat exchanger thermal lines.

Figure 12: The AMS rack before the installation of the air release valve (left). The AMS rack following the installation of the air release valve, indicated by the red arrow (right).

Overheating condensate UV lamp: The small LED UV disinfection light built into the condensate collection lines, although functional, would often overheat and undergo an automatic shutdown. A small CPU fan was added to the front of the UV light and this has subsequently allowed the UV disinfection system to operate continuously since its installation.

Replacement of condensate collection pump: The test phase illustrated improvement potential in the condensate collection pump. The original pump (Elettra 80, Free Water Pump), composed of a physically separated water pump and a level switch (Figure 13), had certain operational issues, including exhibiting a high level of microbial growth within the transparent level switch housing. The pump was subsequently replaced by an Aspen Pumps Mini Tank 1056/2 pump (Figure 13). This pump operated without issue for the remainder of the AIT phase.

Figure 13: AIT phase deployed condensate collection pumps.

Figure 14: Initial AMS condensate pump showing microbial contamination in housing.

Enhanced on-line measurement of AMS performance: Although the AMS contains a wide variety of sensors, a condensate flow meter, in addition to a CO₂ flow meter, were not built into the baseline design of the AMS due to constraints on time and overall system cost. During the AIT phase, additional time could be invested into sensor selection and a condensate flow meter (BIO-TECH, FCH-midi-POM, 503593), and CO₂ flow sensor (SMC PFM750S-C8-A-W) were acquired. The condensate flow meter was built into the AMS and tested during the AIT phase, while the connectors and required wiring for the CO₂ flow sensor were determined and preparations made for the later installation of the CO₂ flow sensor in Antarctica.

Optimization of FEG climate control: The AIT phase provided the first opportunity to integrate the AMS with the thermal control system and the CDHS, to observe if the developed control algorithms were indeed appropriate to maintain the FEG conditions in their desired ranges. Even during its initial operational period the AMS was observed to perform well in maintaining temperature, RH and CO₂ levels in the FEG. That being said, the logic of the temperature and RH control required some adjustments throughout the course of the AIT phase. In conjunction with Argus Control Systems, the team invested a significant amount of work into ensuring the control logic for the AMS was appropriately responding. Further optimization was likely possible but, because the external conditions in Antarctic would be significantly different than the primary Northern Germany spring/summer conditions that the MTF faced during AIT, effort was instead spend on improving other systems. The AIT phase also demonstrated that that FEG humidifier, acquired to aid the FEG in reaching the desired humidity level during the very first few weeks of plant growth before the plants transpire sufficient water, was appropriately sized.

Service Section AMS: The Service Section AMS system was installed near the end of the AIT phase. Each individual component, as well as the control logic, was tested and worked as designed. Although the nominal design of the Service Section AMS included a humidifier to allow the humidity in the Service Section to be raised during the Antarctic deployment phase, a determination was made during the AIT phase that the humidifier would not need to be utilized in Antarctica.

2.2.2 Nutrient Delivery System

The NDS was primarily installed during two different phases, during which the relevant project partner was on-site:

- Oct 17 – Oct 28, 2016
 - Personnel: Work package leader from University of Guelph

- Main activities: NDS rack delivery, installation of NDS rack structure and primary NDS rack elements, dosing pump and pH and EC sensor installation and wiring, initial installation of FEG NDS feed and return lines and pumps
- Mar 18 – Mar 24, 2017
 - Personnel: Work package leader from University of Guelph
 - Main activities: NDS tray installation, sensor installation, FEG piping improvements, testing

As University of Guelph was also responsible for the Argus control system, considerable CDHS activities occurred in tandem to NDS integration and testing. The state of the NDS following the first on-site integration phase is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: The NDS rack following the initial October 2016 installation phase.

The NDS rack nearing the completion of the Bremen test phase is illustrated in Figure 16.

Figure 16: The NDS rack nearing the completion of the AIT phase (Image credit: Liquifer - Bruno Stubenrauch, 2017).

Throughout the AIT phase several improvements were made to the NDS based on the integration of its hardware and operation experience. These include the following items:

Sump pump: The FEG subfloor sump pumps, which collect return nutrient solution before it is pumped back into the NDS tanks, were installed but did not provide sufficient pump head to return this fluid back into the tanks. This resulted in the team changing out the as-ordered pump (Whale, Orca 500) with a large sump pump (Whale, Orca 950) while keeping the sump enclosure box. Additionally there were some reliability issues with the electric field sensor switch in the sump pump enclosure that activates the pump. Likely due to the larger bilge pump, the minimum water level in the sump enclosure box (e.g. after the pump was deactivated) was right on the edge of what could be picked up by the bottom level sensor of the switch and thus would in some instances result in the pump continually activating or the sump box even overflowing. This issue was fixed by raising the level sensor up several millimetres through the installation of several washers under it. The initial installation location of the sump pump electrical box (lying flat directly between the two sump pumps) was also later changed to provide more floor space in the FEG subfloor. This extra floor space in this area (where the bulk of FEG subfloor hardware is located) allows for the on-site operator to more easily repair NDS and thermal control system subfloor equipment.

Figure 17: The FEG subfloor sump pumps and sump pump electrical enclosure box in its final install location.

Light entry into NDS lines: It is well known in the hydroponic community that any light reaching the hydroponic solution can result in microbial growth. This resulted in several minor modifications being implemented to the NDS return and feedline to increase the amount of light blockage. Transparent braided tubing was either changed out or painted over with black paint. The transparent sump pump boxes were covered with aluminum foil, as were the extra access ports that were present in the NDS drain lines in the middle of the FEG. Finally, at the tray to drain pipe interfaces, small adapters were added to further light-tighten the connection.

Improving plant tray designs: Based on the experience gained during the AIT phase, several plant growth tray configurations were modified to provide better consistency with the aeroponic irrigation across the entire plant growth tray area. In particular, the higher density trays had their internal mister arrangements updated to include additional misters. Further, although implemented to a greater degree during the Antarctic deployment, the angles of the plant growth trays were adjusted during the AIT phase to reduce stagnant water within the trays and increase drainage. From the outset this was known to have pros and cons considering that although better drainage was achieved, the increased tray angle also essentially eliminated the final layer of water within the bottom of the trays and thus reduced the buffer of reaction time to any NDS failure (i.e. the extra tray water would otherwise provide the plants with reserve water in the event that nutrient delivery was restricted due to system failure). The 'mass' production of the ca. 50 growth trays (42 plus spares) was also conducted during the AIT phase (Figure 18).

Figure 18: FEG plant growth trays being ‘mass’ produced.

Ozone disinfection improvements: Although the hydroponic solution stayed relatively ‘clean’ through the duration of the AIT phase a few modifications were made to the ozone disinfection system during the AIT phase to further increase its disinfection activity. Firstly several air pumps (KnF, NMP830KNE) were acquired to provide the suction to move the 300 mg/h ozone generated from the (A2Z Ozone, Aquatic 2) ozone generators into the nutrient solution in each respective tank. These air pumps were installed within enclosure boxes to each side of the NDS rack as illustrated in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Install location of the air pumps to deliver ozone to the NDS tanks.

Pinch valve clogging of tubing: it was remarked during the early period of the AIT phase when the NDS was not actively used to provide hydroponic solution (e.g. before the plants were planted), that the tubing that feeds acid and base to the NDS tanks to adjust pH could become clogged. In particular, as this tubing passes through the acid and base dosing pumps and then to pinch valves (Figure 20) which are used to decide which tank is fed with acid or base, and the pinch valves were very seldom used, the pinched plastic tubing was seen on one or two occasions to be fused together as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 20: Top section of the NDS rack above tank 2. Acid and base dosing pumps are obvious in the top left corner of the image. The red arrow indicates the location of the two pinch valves.

Thus closing of the tubing could result in a potentially dangerous safety scenario in which the acid or base dosing pump is activated but the outlet tubing could be fused shut thus leaving no path for the acid or base to pass, possibly causing one of the tubing connections to actually burst and spray acid or base in all directions.

Figure 21: An example of the flexible tubing following long-term installation within the acid/base pinch valve.

To combat this potential safety concern, a checklist item was built into the weekly tasks of the MTF operator to simply remove the tubing from the pinch valves and re-install it with a slightly offset from the previous position. Additionally, a small safety curtain (Figure 22) was installed in front of the NDS rack that provides additional safety for the operator (although safety protocol already has the operator wearing safety glasses when the NDS rack doors are open). Finally, limits on the strength of the acid and base stock solution bottles were imposed in agreement with DLR work place health and safety representatives. It should be recalled that, even though all of these safety precautions were implemented, in a nominally operated MTF (e.g. with growing plants) the pinch valves should be opening and closing on relatively regular occasion and thus the likelihood of the tubing becoming fused together is further reduced.

Figure 22: The NDS rack safety curtain installed in front of the top most section of the NDS rack.

Fresh water and waste water tank enhancements: The AIT phase demonstrated to the EDEN ISS team that, to ensure the quality of the fresh water tank over long periods of time, additional action was required. Thus, a system including a UV light, filter and circulation pump was designed and initially installed (but not fully tested) during the AIT phase. The system included all three items submerged directly into the fresh water tank. A small electrical enclosure box including manual on/off switches for the system was added in the cold porch and safety stickers were placed on the top of the fresh water reservoir access ports (i.e. that the UV light should be turned off prior to operator access to the tank). As it has been seen that the UV LED within the condensate collection system is not completely sufficient to ensure the fresh water within the cold porch remains perfectly clean for long periods, these added units were added for further confidence in water quality.

General items: A number of additional NDS actions were implemented during the AIT phase. These include:

- *Fixing of small leaks in the subfloor.* As would be expected with any complicated network of plastic piping, over the course of the AIT phase several small leaks were found and subsequently sealed / fixed.
- *Troubleshooting the initially installed NDS rack circulation flowmeters.* The initial Atlas Scientific, ½" high precision flow meter could not be successfully wired to the C&DH system without reoccurring issues. Following a sequence of troubleshooting activities, these particular

sensors were abandoned for simple on/off plastic flow switches (Shanghai Yuanben) which worked without issue.

- *Finalized 3D printed parts design.* In addition to the mass production of the plant growth trays, the EDEN ISS team completed the design and produced the custom made 3D printed plant and rockwool holders that would be incorporated into the FEG (Figure 40). These were printed in ABS and PLA using 3D printers at the Institute of Space Systems.

2.2.3 Thermal Control System

The DLR EDEN ISS team had the responsibility for the thermal control system of the MTF. That said, much of the design and, in particular, the manufacture of the system was undertaken by HART Kälte- und Klimatechnik. The integration of the thermal control system occurred via two distinct periods of on-site installation work by HART in conjunction with the DLR team:

- Jan 11, 2017 – Delivery of the thermal control system rack and freecooler.
 - Personnel: HART technician
 - Main activities: Installation of the thermal system rack and roof mounted freecooler. Piping connections between the thermal system rack and external free cooler. Test connection, including circulation of cooling fluid in through the freecooler (which was not used for the AIT phase due to the warm external temperatures in Germany in comparison to Antarctica).
- Off and on from Jan through to March, 2017 – LED and ISPR thermal lines
 - Personnel: HART technician
 - Main activities: LED thermal line installation, ISPR thermal line installation, leak testing (commenced Mar 20, 2017). Delivery of external AC machine (Mar 1, 2017).

The thermal control rack in its as-delivered status and post-integration are illustrated in Figure 23.

Figure 23: The thermal control system in its as-delivered configuration (left). The thermal control system following installation into the Service Section (right).

Due to the temperatures in Bremen, Germany being relatively warm in comparison to Antarctica, an external AC unit (Figure 24) was acquired and installed adjacent to the MTF to serve as a source for the cold cooling fluid required to cool internal MTF equipment. Although not used for more than an initial test to verify overall function and that no leakage existed in the cooling lines running external to the MTF, the free cooler to be employed in Antarctica was installed onto the roof of the MTF for the AIT phase (Figure 24).

Figure 24: The external AC unit for the cooling of the EDEN ISS MTF during the AIT phase (left). The roof-mounted free cooler being removed from the MTF at the completion of the AIT phase (right).

The long duration AIT test phase was able to provide the EDEN ISS team useful experience on the thermal control system and its operations that could be carried into the Antarctic test phase as well as serve for future design considerations. These included:

Rack accessibility: Likely the most important thing learned from the operations of the thermal control system, is that a better trade off with limiting overall system volume and maintenance/accessibility likely could have been had. Indeed having been able to fit all of the various thermal control system components in such a small volume was an accomplishment itself, but such component density resulted in access issues. Of note was wiring of certain components, in particular those at the back of the rack. When issues arose the amount of time required to find appropriate ways to access parts, remove screws holding enclosure boxes shut and simply seeing in an easy manner if the e.g. pump/mixing valve was operational was sometimes difficult. Additionally, with the tight curves in the thermal system piping sometimes troubleshooting was slowed as following a given outlet and correlating that with the technical drawings of the system proved challenging. In future designs, the team would certainly allow the thermal rack volume to expand for some added accessibility to components in the rack itself.

Network of LED cooling lines: The work effort to install and subsequently remove leakage from all points within the FEG LED cooling line network proved to be a much higher work effort than originally planned. Although the racks were 'standard' the small sizing differences and other installed parts resulted in essentially every thermal line running to an LED to be custom sized and built. This was followed by a number of days being required to seal up the initial leaks discovered in the system

following the first filling of the system with water. Additional leaks (although small) would also surface over the first few months of operations. Although flow shut-off valves were installed before and after each set of two LEDs, if a leak was indeed found in either one of the main horizontal or vertical LED cooling lines, the entire left or right hand side of the FEG's LED cooling system would need to be shut down for the repair and subsequent drying of the PVC cement. Thus the future LED cooling network should have additional cut-off valves, in particular one for each of the eight grow racks, to allow more of the LED system to remain active during times of needed repair.

Several other design changes and improvements were built into the system during AIT phase. These included:

- Addition of Gardena quick connectors to various cooling fluid filling locations in the FEG to improve filling and air-release from the system.
- Addition of a subfloor heater within the FEG. As seen in Figure 25 the heater was installed in the vicinity of the FEG emergency exit door. This heater served both as a supplement to the AMS rack heaters while at the same time focusing heat on two areas that are considered a concern for very cold temperatures (the FEG subfloor area itself and the potential freezing of the FEG emergency exit door).

Figure 25: The installed subfloor heater near the FEG emergency exit door.

2.2.4 CDH System

The initial install of the CDH system was completed during the on-site visit of the work package leader, University of Guelph. This occurred in two distinct phases:

- Oct 17 – Oct 28, 2016
 - Personnel: Work package leader from University of Guelph
 - Main activities: Mounting of the Argus enclosure box into the Service Section, initial wiring of sensors actuators
- Mar 18 – Mar 24, 2017
 - Personnel: Work package leader from University of Guelph
 - Main activities: Continued wiring and general Argus system troubleshooting.

That said, considerable work was conducted by the DLR team to get the CDH system operational and this work continued up until the weeks before the facility was shipped to Antarctica. Argus Control Systems (manufacturer) was also very active in system troubleshooting and making enhancements

throughout the AIT phase. Another major activity associated with the C&DH system during the AIT phase was the setup of the DLR Mission Control Center (Figure 6). Figure 26 presents a comparison of the Argus box soon after delivery to DLR Bremen and the box nearing the completion of the AIT phase.

Figure 26: The Argus system near the outset of the AIT phase (left). The Argus system nearing the completion of the AIT phase (right).

Argus box modifications: In addition to the normal wiring, configuration and testing of the Argus system, a wide amount of both pre-planned upgrades, as well as enhancements made due to experience gained during the AIT phase, were implemented. Several of the top-level changes include:

- Installation of a physical switch for the full on/off of the Argus box. A toggle switch was added to the top of the Argus box to give the operator the chance to power cycle the Argus box should a hard power cycle be required. This was an improvement on the as-designed system in which main power for the Argus box was directly wired to the uninterruptible power supply. In certain instances the plugging-in or removal of power by pulling-out this power cable resulted in a less than 'clean' cut of power and sometimes resulted in a fuse in the Argus box being burnt.
- Addition of supplementary power supplies. Two additional power converters were added to the Argus box. A 230 VAC to 24 VDC power supply (DNR120AS24-I, XP Power) and a 230 VAC to 24 VAC transformer (8802618, RS Pro) as shown in the top right corner of the right side image in Figure 26.
- Terminal blocks and additional sensor connections. To improve the organization of sensor cabling, in particular for the sensors connected to the Modbus network, an additional set of terminal blocks were added to the right hand side of the Argus box. As several sensors required their sensor cable to be terminated with a resistor, several small enclosure boxes for these sensors were added into the bottom of the Argus box.

- NDS flow meter sensor wiring. Although seemingly straightforward, the wiring for the initially installed NDS flow meters (previously described in the NDS section) proved to be difficult and resulted in several corrective actions such as the changing out of one of the Argus Titan IO modules, replacement of numerous transient voltage suppressors, and use of other power supplies. Unfortunately, in the end a different model flow meter was required.
- Leak sensor wiring: Troubleshooting was also required to get the FEG and Service Section leak sensors working in a reliable manner. The wiring was changed on several occasions during the AIT phase and the reliability of the sensors improved. That said, the wiring was changed for a final time during the Antarctic deployment phase.
- Fan into Argus Server cabinet: A small computer was added during the AIT phase for additional cooling of the CDHS server cabinet above the ISPR.

2.2.5 Power System

The power box was the first subsystem to be mechanically installed within the MTF. In particular, the power box was installed into the Service Section before the two EDEN ISS containers were integrated together. Thus the power box installation occurred on Oct 7, 2016. The main activities associated with the power system following the power box installation was the wiring of the relevant EDEN ISS components to the terminal blocks within the box and the installation of the power monitoring system. An early view into the power box is provided in Figure 28. The uninterruptible power supply was installed the week of Oct 31, 2016.

Figure 28: A view into the power box during the early phase of the AIT phase.

Overall MTF design changes and experience during the AIT phase resulted in several updates being made to the power system prior to the Antarctic deployment phase. In particular the following items were implemented:

- Laid several additional (unplanned) cables and reorganized the breakers and connections within the power box itself.

- Installed a 12 VDC power converter for Argus system connected smoke detectors (i.e. so that the smoke detector signal could be transmitted to the NM-III and over telemetry to the EDEN ISS MCC).
- Initial testing of the energy measurement system.

2.2.6 Plant Health Imaging System

Following laboratory-based tests of various cameras and imaging systems conducted by Telespazio and DLR, the DLR team installed and tested the selected cameras and imaging hardware within the MTF. The primary work on the camera system was conducted in March 2017. In addition, researchers from the University of Florida visited Bremen on April 12-14, 2017 and in June 2017 to install and test the multi wavelength imagers. Figure 29 shows a view into the FEG racks showing the location of some of the Plant Health Monitoring System cameras.

Figure 29: Locations of FEG cameras on the north side of the FEG.

The installation of the cameras proceeded as planned and, besides the needed replacement of one or two cameras, did not result in any significant problems. During the AIT phase, several modified GoPros for multi wavelength imaging of specific crops were installed and tested. One of the installed cameras is shown in Figure 30. The install of the multi wavelength imagers also proceeded smoothly but raised several items which provided benefit for the Antarctic operations phase. These included:

- Working out connectivity issues between the imagers and the MTF wireless network.
- Converging on the solution to power the imagers using a Power-over-Ethernet to USB converter adapter. Previously a USB charging device was purchased to serve as charging hub in which all the FEG imagers could be connected but this did not charge the imagers.
- Installation of measurement stickers and calibration targets within the field-of-view of the imagers (scales were also installed for the nominal plant health monitoring cameras).

Figure 30: One of several multi wavelength imagers from the University of Florida installed within the FEG.

2.2.7 Illumination System

The EDEN ISS illumination system, manufactured by Heliospectra, was delivered to DLR Bremen on Nov 14, 2016 (Figure 31).

Figure 31: The Heliospectra LEDs just following delivery to DLR Bremen.

The installation of the LEDs within the FEG went proceeded without issue. That said, the long duration AIT test phase was able to surface a few issues and allowed these issues to be worked out before the Antarctic test phase. These included:

LED cooling fluid leaks: It was remarked that once cooling fluid (100% water during the early portion of AIT phase – April 2017) was added to the LED thermal lines that several of the LED panels had leaks and that the cooling fluid was leaking into the internal LED housing (Figure 32). There was obvious leakage in three to four of the LEDs but a decision was made, in correspondence with Heliospectra, that the LED cooling line adapters should all be replaced.

Figure 32: Two different FEG LEDs with an obvious amount of cooling fluid contained within, during the AIT phase.

With the old LED connectors, water was able to get out of the system at the interface where the connector connected to the copper pipe that runs through the actual LED panel. As the copper is not perfectly flat and can have some micro-cracks on its surface, water could get through the seals. The connectors were changed to have a compression fitting (the primary disadvantage being that the new connectors cannot be removed again from the LED panels as they are compression fit on). A visual comparison of the old and new LED connectors is illustrated in Figure 33.

Figure 33: The old LED connectors and the replacement connector assemblies so as to reduce the likelihood of leaks within the LED cooling water network.

With the new LED connector assemblies, no additional cooling fluid leaks were observed at or within the LEDs.

Installation of LED light bars: Three LED bars were installed within the cucumber chamber as illustrated in Figure 34. These bars were an add-on to the overhead lighting used throughout the FEG. An electrical enclosure box was installed in the vicinity of the chamber and control of the bars is via manual switch or on a desired on/off frequency. Although not required for cucumber growth the bars were

installed as means to further investigate the idea of lighting directly within the canopy and the pros and cons of such systems.

Figure 34: One of three LED bars (indicated by red arrow) installed horizontally in the canopy of the cucumber chamber.

The LED system performed very well during the AIT phase and no panel required change-out. That said, the AIT phase allowed the Argus LED control to be formed into a much more user friendly interface. Additionally, the team garnered experience in ensuring that air was suitably removed from the thermal lines, as in some instances removing the air from the eight distinct high points (eight racks) was not always trivial and the LEDs would overheat and shutoff via the built in software shutoff or via their thermal switch embedded in the panel themselves. A good technique and protocol was developed to remove air from the LED thermal lines.

The AIT phase was also utilized as a means to collect precise light quality and quantity data at various locations (e.g. tray positions and for tall, medium and short growth trays) and feed in the results in to the adjustment of the specific intensities of the four distinct LED wavelengths of the panels. The methodology of these tests along with the full set of results are not described here but rather in the final lighting system design document (*EDEN ISS-HS-WP3.4-D3.9-LS Design Document-v2.2*). Light measurements were initially conducted by scientists from Wageningen University (May 2017) and then later by personnel from Heliospectra (June 2017) as shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Illumination system measurements conducted by Heliospectra within the FEG in June 2017.

2.2.8 Structure / Interface

The great deal of the MTF structure installation work was conducted during the container manufacturing at CBG. This included the bulk of the work to install the racks within the FEG. The Service Section racks were primarily the responsibility of subsystem partners but additional aluminum profiles and mounting structure were installed in the Service Section throughout the AIT phase. A large emphasis was also placed upon enhancing the appearance as well of the ergonomics of the interior of the MTF. This effort was led LIQUIFER Systems Group and DLR Bremen. Several design modifications were made throughout the AIT phase. A discussion of a subset of those related to the structure of the MTF:

Service Section to FEG door: Following the container manufacturing process, it was found that the available space between the Service Section and FEG was less than had been foreseen in the design. Despite the implemented design tolerances this resulted in the Service Section to FEG door striking the NDS rack when it was opened (previous location of this collision is illustrated in Figure 36). This resulted in the NDS rack having to be reduced in width by several centimetres. Thankfully, margin was built into the NDS rack that this was possible and the NDS rack subsystem lead was able to adjust the rack design. It was noted that the door had sufficient clearance to the rack at the bottom, but touched the rack at the top, when opened, which is assumed to be due to twisting of the containers during transport and installation. For future designs, additional margin will be put on the design tolerances, to account for this possibility.

Figure 36: FEG to Service Section door and the NDS rack corner.

Leak/condensate at container interface: During the colder days of winter during the AIT phase water was collecting at the Service Section to FEG container interface. This resulted in the manufacture of a small metal collection basin that was later installed into the ceiling at the container interface. The principle was that if any water condensate was collected in this area of the container interface it would fill the shallow basin and then flow down a specific outlet path to a location outside the container (rather than collecting in the internal area of the container interface). This work effort proved useful and no additional water was observed in the interface area. That said, further design changes (including the removal of the shallow basin) were later implemented upon arrival in Antarctica.

FEG floor grates size: Considering how frequent access to the FEG subfloor was required, and the fact that the MTF is typically operated with a single operator, it was decided approximately halfway into the AIT phase that the size of the FEG floor panels should be reduced. Originally the FEG had four corridor floor panels running the length of the FEG. These were modified to approximately half their original size to have eight total panels along the FEG corridor (Figure 37). These panels were more appropriate in terms of size and mass for installation and removal by a single operator and reduce considerably the overall workload should any repairs or maintenance be required in the FEG sub-floor.

Figure 37: FEG large floor grates (left). FEG small floor grates (right).

2.2.9 ISPR

The lessons learned associated with the RUCOLA ISPR full-rack plant growth system are described in the ISPR Test Results document (D4.1) and the ISPR Performance document, which will be included in the Overall system performance document (D5.11).

2.2.10 Misc.

The EDEN ISS team developed several other pieces of hardware and tools during the AIT phase that will benefit the project during the operations phase in Antarctica. One tool in particular is the trolley (Figure 38). The trolley was developed as a mobile work space and tool carrier for use in the FEG. Its three levels are each sized to the standard 40 x 60 cm European pallets used as grow trays. Although the trolley was constructed with several basic concepts in the mind, the trolley underwent considerable modification during the AIT phase as things were learned about blockage in the FEG corridor, what tools and consumables would be best stored in the trolley and what would be best stored elsewhere, etc.

Figure 38: The FEG trolley nearing the end of the AIT phase.

Work was also spent on defining how the storage cabinets should be designed and how the specific storage space could best be used. Various options were tested out during the AIT test phase. One particular area of interest was the storage cabinet within the cold porch (Figure 39).

Figure 39: The cold porch storage cabinet (drawers and cabinets on the left hand side with open shelves on the right hand side).

2.3 Test Phase

2.3.1 Description of the Test Phase

The assembly and integration of the containers and the different subsystems was carried out between October 2016 and April 2017 following which the MTF was ready for integrated testing and crop growth could commence. A total of 15 different crop types were cultivated in the MTF during the system test and grow-out phase between April and September 2017. These crops ranged from Swiss chard and various lettuce cultivars to cucumber, pepper and tomato. For select crops, such as herbs and radishes, seeding was done directly onto fiber mats, but for easy transfer between the nursery area and the dedicated plant cultivation levels, most of the plants were seeded in rockwool cubes which were placed in specially designed 3D-printed rockwool holders. Compare Figure 40 (Bottom, left). For medium and large crops (e.g., cucumber, pepper), an additional support structure was included, to provide some support to the plants during the initial grow phase. The 3D-printed structures can be seen in Figure 40 (Top). A typical root system that was created within the aeroponic trays can be seen in Figure 40 (Bottom, right).

Figure 40: Rockwool holder with support structure (top). Rockwool holder with inserted rockwool cube (bottom, left). Typical root system (bottom, right).

During the system test phase, various tests were performed to determine the optimal MTF system settings and their respective performance characteristics. For example, light measurements were performed to fine-tune the spectral quality and power settings of the LED panels in the different plant cultivation racks. A dedicated safety inspection of the facility was also performed, as well as measurements of the noise level in the containers under various operational scenarios. The worst case noise levels in the Service Section and the FEG are listed in Table 1. In all cases the noise level is below the levels at which hearing protection would be suggested or mandatory (80 and 85 dB respectively) for facility operators according to German law.

Table 1: Worst case noise levels in the Service Section and the FEG.

Frequency (Hz)	Service Section (dB)	FEG (dB)
63	63.57	60.76
125	64.04	66.32
250	60.1	59.51
500	55	62.75
1000	44.68	56.88
2000	41.89	52.82
4000	35.71	48.45
8000	32.69	39.03

Figure 41: Detailed acoustic test results (dB on y-axis) at different frequencies for three different test cases within the Service Section (main MTF work area).

Aside from the tests which were performed to validate and characterize the functioning of the different subsystems and components, the test phase was also used to develop and check various operational aspects, such as microbial sampling, biomass sampling, cleaning and decontamination procedures and remote control operations which will be used during the actual operations phase in the Antarctic.

A dedicated Mission Control Center (MCC) has been built at DLR Bremen which will be used to communicate with crew in Antarctica and allow remote observation and control of MTF parameters and set-points. During the test phase, communication between the MTF and the MCC was established via patch antennas, enabling the transfer of camera images and telemetry data. During the operational phase in Antarctica, the MTF will transfer data via a fiber optic cable to Neumayer Station III (with a patch antenna serving as a backup), after which the data is transferred via satellite to Germany.

Figure 42: Interior of the FEG at the end of the test phase in Bremen, Germany.

A final harvest was conducted at the end of the test phase, in preparation of the facility cleaning and packing procedures prior to transport. Figure 42 shows the interior of the FEG some days prior to this harvest event, with the system nearly at full capacity and most of the plants in a fully matured state. Roughly 23 kg of edible biomass was obtained from the MTF during this final harvest, with approximately 25% of this harvest used for food safety and quality tests.

Plasticizer contamination: A subset of food safety test results is presented below, in Table 2, along with the tolerable daily intake levels for various phthalate plasticizers for a person weighing 60 kg (Schäfer, 2013). Based on the test results, the overwintering crew in the Antarctic should be able to safely consume the produce from the MTF without any health risks due to MTF equipment/construction materials. Additional testing will be carried out during the operational phase to verify the consistency of these results throughout the life cycle of the facility.

Table 2: Phthalate contamination levels in edible biomass samples.

Phthalate	Leafy Greens (mg/kg)	Tomato, Pepper, Cucumber (mg/kg)	Tolerable Daily Intake (mg/day)
Di-butylphthalate	<0.1	<0.1	0.6
Di-ethylhexylphthalate	<0.1	<0.1	3.0
Di-iso-nonylphthalate	<0.5	<0.5	9.0
Di-iso-decylphthalate	<0.5	<0.5	9.0
Benzyl-butylphthalate	<0.1	<0.1	30.0

FEG air flow rate measurements: A series of air flow rate tests were performed to determine the optimal AMS rack fan power settings. A Trotec anemometer was used to measure air speeds. At a fan setting of 70% the total measured flow rate was 1374 m³/h which matched well with the desired target of 1400 m³/h and thus 70% was used as the baseline setpoint of the system (best balance between pressure loss, flow rate and power consumption). At this setting, the distribution between the left and right side was well balanced with values of 683 m³/h and 691 m³/h, respectively.

Additionally, the air flow was measured at the louvers at a distance of ca. 1-2 cm from the louver exits (Figure 43). In addition to further confirming the flow consistency of flow throughout the FEG, these tests provided initial quantitative results related to the target air flow rate at the canopy itself.

Figure 43: Trotec anemometer used in the FEG air flow measurements.

The results of these louver air flow tests for the various locations tested are shown in Table 3. It should be noted that all of these results were obtained with fully open louvers and that for further flow balancing and adjustment each individual louver can itself be opened or closed to different degrees.

Table 3: Measured air speeds at the louver exits for four different locations and four different levels for each side of the FEG.

		Air speed at the louver outlet m/sec								Average	Theoret.
Left side		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8		
A	1 th	0,6		0,7		0,6		0,5		0,60	0,54
B	2 th	0,9		0,5		0,7		0,4		0,63	0,54
C	3 th	0,7		0,5		0,6		0,5		0,58	0,54
D	4 th	0,5		0,5		0,8		0,6		0,60	0,54
Right side											
A	1 th	0,35		0,4		0,6		0,8		0,54	0,54
B	2 th	0,86		0,35		0,6		0,6		0,60	0,54
C	3 th	0,7		0,6		0,7		0,6		0,65	0,54
D	4 th	0,6		0,6		0,8		0,4		0,60	0,54

FEG atmospheric closure: The FEG atmospheric closure was also tested via a leakage test using CO₂ as a tracer gas. The results can be used to estimate the air exchange between the FEG internal environment and the surrounding environment (in particular the greatest amount of leakage is expected between the FEG and the Service Section separation wall/door). The leakage test was conducted by increasing the CO₂ concentration within the FEG and watching the decay of the concentration with time. These tests were conducted without plants in the FEG, all MTF internal and external doors closed and at nominal air circulation rates within the AMS rack (70% fan setting). The results of one of the tests conducted at the end of May 2017 are illustrated in Figure 44.

Figure 44: Results of an end of May 2017 FEG leakage test.

These results equate to approximately 0.143 air exchanges per hour in the FEG (or 343% leakage per day). This leakage value is less than the 500% leakage per day used as a top-level design specification. It should also be noted that the obtained results represent the worst case closure of the system as the tests conducted during the AIT phase were conducted without fully insulating the container to container interfaces, without fully closing the cable channel link between the FEG and Service Section, without taping and insulating the AMS air ducts and without a final improvement of the seal of the FEG to Service Section door itself. Leakage tests were repeated in Antarctica and those updated results should take precedence over these presented here, as representative of the final system.

Nutrient solution recipe adjustments: During the AIT phase grow-outs, several of the fruit crops demonstrated an iron deficiency. In conjunction with scientists from Wageningen the hydroponic nutrient solution recipe for the fruit crops was adjusted to increase the iron concentration by an additional 33%. Following these adjustments no additional signs of iron deficiencies were observed in any of the crops.

2.3.2 Mission Preparation Steps and Transport

From project inception, the EDEN ISS project always worked with a hard 'launch' date. In addition to being analogous to a space mission the 'launch' date represented the once a year date that large equipment destined for Antarctica could be put on a ship for transport to Antarctica. Ship access to Antarctica is only available during the Austral summer and if this window would be missed, then the project would need to wait a subsequent year for shipment to Antarctica. The launch date at which the EDEN ISS containers would be picked up from the DLR Institute of Space Systems was set as October 2, 2017. The overall transport chain to Antarctica followed the following pathway:

- October 2, 2017: Truck pickup of the three EDEN ISS containers at the DLR, Institute of Space Systems in Bremen and shipment to Hamburg harbor.
- October 9, 2017: Loading of the EDEN ISS containers onto the Golden Karoo container ship in Hamburg for ship transport to Cape Town, South Africa (Figure 45).

- November 9, 2017: Arrival of the Golden Karoo in Cape Town, South Africa and subsequent offloading of the EDEN ISS containers.
- December 1, 2017: Loading of the EDEN ISS containers onto the South African research vessel, S.A. Agulhas II for transport to vicinity of NM-III in Antarctica (departure from Cape Town December 8, 2017) (Figure 45).
- January 3, 2018: Arrival of the S.A. Agulhas II in the NM-III vicinity and offloading of the EDEN ISS containers onto the sea ice for tracked vehicle transport to NM-III.

Figure 45: (Left) Loading of the EDEN ISS containers onto the Golden Karoo container ship in Hamburg, Germany (Photo credit: DLR/Hafenspedition). (Right) EDEN ISS containers on the S.A. Agulhas in Antarctic water (Photo credit: Will Jelbert).

The three EDEN ISS 20-foot shipping containers shipped to Antarctic included: the Service Section container, the FEG container and a standard transport container used to bring consumables, external MTF hardware and spare parts of the project. All three of these containers had to undergo a number of steps to prepare them for shipment. This involved the general sequence of events of; removing externally installed hardware (free cooler, external lights, antenna, etc.), the de-integration and separation of the Service Section and FEG containers, the removal of internally installed hardware considered fragile, the securing of the remainder of the installed internal hardware, the general cleaning of the facility, and the disinfection of the Service Section and FEG containers.

Container De-Integration

External hardware from the EDEN ISS containers was removed so that the facility could be transported as per standard shipping containers. That said, the Service Section and FEG containers were transported as 'general cargo' and did not have to meet the most stringent Convention for Safe Container (CSC) tests which are particularly relevant related to stacking of containers during storage or shipment. Although this restricted how the custom containers would be transported on the various ships, it reduced cost and certification requirements. Such a decision should be an early decision point for others considering employing shipping containers in their greenhouse or facility designs. The de-integration of the containers was the next hurdle in shipment preparation and because the activities would essentially be repeated in reverse upon arrival of the containers in the Antarctica, the team further documented the de-integration steps as they were being conducted and stored all hardware into two main tool chests so that all bolts, fasteners and other hardware could be easily found and accessed in Antarctica. De-integration involved the following main actions:

- Disconnecting all power and sensor cabling from the power box and Argus control box for those devices that were connected directly from these locations to a place in the FEG container
- Disconnection of the two feed and two return lines for the nutrient delivery system
- Disconnection of the feed and return lines for the thermal control system cooling lines running to the LEDs

- Disconnection and storage for shipment of the 16 (eight each side) air management system flexible ducts
- Removal of ceiling, sidewall and floor panels around the container to container interface
- Removal of the four primary structural bolts holding the two containers together
- Use of a crane to separate the containers
- Installation of a transport wall onto the open side of each of the two containers

Container Shipping Masses

During this separation operation (September 13, 2017) the Service Section and FEG container were weighed to help the team further ensure that the container transport masses stayed below the 10 ton limit of the NM-III on-site crane that would be used to lift the containers onto the elevated platform. This weighing would also help dictate if additional project supplies could be shipped directly into the Service Section or FEG containers or if all project supplies would be shipped within the blue transport container. On this date, the Service Section container had a mass of 9.7 tons (metric) and the FEG container had a mass of 7.7 tons. All EDEN ISS containers were subsequently reweighed on October 2nd in their final shipping configuration. The Service Section container, which included no additional boxes, had a mass of 9.6 tons, the FEG container, including 16 shipping boxes, had a mass of 8.5 tons, while the blue transport container which included the remainder of the EDEN ISS project supplies (122 items/boxes) had a mass of 6.2 tons.

Spares, Packaging, Cleaning

Overall, the project shipped 138 items with the three containers and subsequently shipped another six boxes via air transport from Cape Town to Antarctica and another six boxes on the German Polarstern icebreaker which was planned to arrive near the end of January 2018 (too late for the EDEN ISS containers). The bulk of these items were metal Zarges boxes filled with consumables and replacement parts. The project had conducted a detailed spares analysis based on a Failure Modes, Effects and Criticality Analysis (FMECA) and acquired replacement parts for as many subsystems as possible. Each shipping box was inventoried and the compiled electronic inventory was a useful on-site reference in Antarctica for the deployment team to find any required hardware. The required dangerous goods (nutrient salts, acid, base, CO₂, calibration gases, cleaning supplies, batteries and construction materials) were further documented and boxed up by a professional shipping company before being distributed between the FEG container and the blue transport container to satisfy safe storage requirements. No styrofoam packing peanuts were used in any of the EDEN ISS boxes to limit the risk of polluting the Antarctic environment. Once the bulk of the packaging was complete, the EDEN ISS containers were cleaned and the Service Section and FEG containers were disinfected using the project developed disinfection system, TransMADDS. In particular, the EDEN ISS team drained all fluids from all systems (e.g., nutrient delivery system, thermal control system, the atmospheric management system, the general sink and water lines as well as the fresh water and waste water tanks in the cold porch) and used a bleach solution to clean the tanks and supply and drain lines. This was followed by vacuuming up any debris within the facility and then a manual surface cleaning using mikrozid AF (Schülke) and paper towels. Subsequently the TransMADDS disinfection system with a 12% hydrogen peroxide solution was used in both the Service Section and FEG containers to clean surfaces that would otherwise not be accessible using its fine mist generator (see Figure 46).

Figure 46: Cleaning with the FEG with the TransMADDS prior to the shipment of the MTF to Antarctica.

This was followed by the installation of blue and yellow sticky card pest traps. All of these actions helped ensure that upon arrival in Antarctica the facility could be re-started in the completely clean state, while at the same time helping to better ensure that the project would live up to its Antarctic Treaty commitments through the German Environmental Agency (Umweltbundesamt) and reduce the likelihood of the introduction of any non-native species.

Temperature during Shipment

Although estimates were made on the temperature environment that the EDEN ISS containers and equipment contained within would be exposed to in their shipment from Bremen, Germany to Neumayer Station III in Antarctica, several temperature loggers (Extech TH10) were installed within the containers prior to shipment. The temperature log over the shipment to Antarctica can be seen in Figure 47.

Figure 47: Plot of EDEN ISS transport temperature during transport to Antarctica.

As seen from

Figure 47 the EDEN ISS containers and hardware were exposed to temperatures between just below 0°C and just above 30°C during their transit from Bremen to NM-III. One temperature maximum approaching 30°C occurred when the Golden Karoo transited over the equatorial regions while the actual maximum occurred just after loading onto the S.A. Agulhas while the ship was still in harbour in Cape Town. Their placement on the deck of the S.A. Agulhas (Figure 45) also meant that the containers were cooled close to ambient temperatures during the Antarctic transit phase as is evident in Figure 47. These plots better help logistics planning for later project years where the transport temperature and durations can be better estimated for future equipment or project consumable shipments.

3 Conclusions

The AIT phase in Bremen was a labour intensive period that involved the expertise of a wide number of EDEN ISS partners but that, without question, benefited the project in an invaluable manner. Without the design changes and experience gained during long duration AIT phase it is likely that a successful Antarctic deployment phase would not have been possible. The bulk of the issues and design changes discussed in this report strengthen the reliability of the MTF system and further improve the scientific output potential of this unique facility and the EDEN ISS project in general.

References

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